

A Study on Growth of Goods and Services Tax (GST) in India - An Innovative Instrument for Indian Corporate Sectors

Dr. P. Govindan

Assistant Professor in Commerce, Department of Commerce,
K.S.Rangasamy College of Arts and Science (Autonomous),
Tiruchengode 637 215, Namakkal, Tamil Nadu, India
E-mail : pgovind.cwa@gmail.com, pgovind.cma@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The main objective of this research is to investigate that the revenue collection of Goods and Service Tax (GST) month wise and its growth. It also examines that total number of 3 (b) and GSTR 1 return filed in Goods and Service Tax (GST) month, quarter wise and its growth rates as on 28.02.2019 in India. This study used secondary data. This study used descriptive statistical tools used such as tables, charts, percentage analysis for analysis and interpretation of data. Inferential statistical tools used such as correlation, paired t test to test various hypotheses of the study. The study period covered since its implementation to as on 28.02.2019. This results of study indicated that total number of 1, 28, 14,377 GST tax payer and totally 18, 11,442(Rs in Thousand Crore) collected India as on 28.02.2019. Out of twenty months positive growth having in eleven month and negative growth having nine months compared with previous month collections. This study finally suggested that government of India, ministry of finance, ministry of commerce and various State/UT governments to take necessary reforms in GST registrations, filing of GST return, payment of tax, refund, interest, penalty and various types GST exemptions different type of tax payers. It is finally concluded that the introduction of GST in India has replaced all indirect taxes in one tax and common market for entire nation it will bring positive energy for entrepreneurs for starting new business ventures in India.

Key Words: GST, Tax, Finance, Tax Payers, Indirect Tax

1.1 Introduction

Taxation in India is entrenched from the period of Manu Smriti and Arthashastra. Present Indian tax system is based on this ancient tax system which was based on the theory of maximum social welfare. It is an obligatory liability for every citizen of the country. This policies play an important role on the economy. Traditionally India's tax regime relied heavily on indirect taxes. Revenue from indirect taxes was the major source of tax revenue till tax reforms were undertaken during nineties. India has seen a number of tax reforms in the past two decades. The concept of Goods and Service Tax (GST) is one of the biggest revolutions in decades around the world. Value added tax was first introduced by Maurice Laure, a French economist, in 1954. GST was originated in France in 1954 and spread of Value Added Tax (VAT) or Goods and Services Tax (GST) system of Indirect taxes across the globe is showing an increasing trend with more than 160 countries. It is the most logical steps towards the comprehensive indirect tax reform in our country since independence. It is a major reform in tax structure.

It is an indirect tax which will subsume almost all the indirect taxes of central government and states governments into a unified tax. To remove cascading effect of taxes and provide a common nation-wide market for goods and services, India is moving towards introduction of Goods and Services Tax (GST). GST will merge all Indirect Taxes under an umbrella single tax. GST is expected to create a common market across the country and accelerate economic growth. The expected benefits of GST include widening of the tax base of both Centre and states and significant improvement in the ease of doing business. GST is also beneficial for

consumers as there would be only one tax from the manufacturers and service providers to the consumer leading to transparency and efficiency. It will prevent leakages from the system and provide relief in terms of reduced tax burden on most of the commodities, brings a new wave of economic reform in the country and help in improving tax governance in India.

1.2 Importance and significance of the study

The historic GST or goods and services tax has become a reality of the new tax system was launched at a function in Central Hall of Parliament on 1st July, 2017. It is a single indirect tax for the whole nation, one which will make India a unified common market. It is the survival of the India's economy in the face of increasing international competition consequent to globalization and liberalization and GST have a positive impact on various sectors and industry for tax reform would be to address the problems of the current system. The impact of GST on inflation depends also on the change in tax rates due to the introduction of the new tax regime. The goods and services tax law in India is a comprehensive, multi-stage, destination-based tax that is levied on every value addition &. It is levied by both the national and the state governments.

Indian taxing system is undergoing revolutionary change today. Tax is one of the most important sources of revenue to the Government and at the same time one of the deciding parameter for economic growth. The fundamental aim of GST is to make uniform the scattered indirect tax system in India and avoid the cascading effect in taxation. The impact going to make by GST will be a transformation in the entire tax system by simplify the indirect tax regime in India. It is an instrument in the indirect tax system of the country. GST is a destination based consumption tax and would be applicable on the supply of goods or services as against the earlier concept of tax on the manufacture or sale of goods or provision of services. This means that tax would accrue to the State or the Union Territory where the consumption takes place. In this surrounding this present is essential to identify the total revenue collection of Goods and Service Tax (GST) month wise, quarter wise and total number of various types of total registered tax payers as on 28th February, 2019.

1.3 Review of literature

Sachin Abda (2017), found that comparing challenges with its advantages, it is clearly visible that its advantages are more compared to challenges. **Mohapatra et al., (2018)**, concluded that there is still a lack of awareness about the new tax reform. **Mohamad et al., (2016)**, findings indicated that the level of awareness of the GST is still not reached a satisfactory level. **Pallavi Chaturvedi et al., (2017)**, concluded that GST will give a major boost to the 'Make in India' initiative of the Government of India. **Azharuddin Mohammad Mussaiyib (2016)**, concluded that GST will strengthen the tax system of India and will impact various industries in a positive manner. **Chandu Ravi Kumar (2015)**, found that significantly help in removing economic biases caused by present complex tax structure. **Dash (2017)**, Results Indicated that the Impact the GST we need to wait for the time and the Government needs to communicate more and more about the systems. In these surroundings the present investigation differs from the early researches in different approaches and contributed the existing literature.

1.4 Research Methodology used

The research study is based on the secondary data collected from various national and international

articles, journals, working papers and various government ministries and websites. This study used to descriptive statistical tools used such as tables, charts, percentage analysis for analysis and interpretation of data. Inferential statistical tools used such as correlation, paired t test to test various hypotheses of the study. The study period covered since its implementation to as on 28.02.2019.

1.5 Objectives of the study

The following are the objectives of the present study.

1. To study on total revenue collection of Goods and Service Tax (GST) month wise and its growth rates as on 28th February, 2019.
2. To examine the total number of 3 (b) and GSTR 1 returns filed in Goods and Service Tax (GST) month wise and its growth rates as on 28.02.2019.
3. To investigate the total number of 3 (b), GSTR 1 and GSTR 4 returns filed in Goods and Service Tax (GST) month, quarter wise and its growth rates as on 28.02.2019.

2. Descriptive statistical tools Results -Analysis and interpretation of data

2.1 Registration of Goods and Service Tax (GST) As on 28th February, 2019

Table 1 : Registration of Goods and Service Tax (GST) As on 28th February, 2019

S. No.	Details	As on 28.02.2019
1	No. of transited (migrated) taxpayers	66,25,077
2	Total No. of new applications received for registration	74,89,804
3	No. of applications approved	63,82,804
4	No. of applications rejected	10,53,602
5	No. of taxpayers who have opted for composition scheme	17,74,379
6	Total No. of taxpayers; new + migrated (1 + 3)	1,28,14,377

Source: www.cbic.gov.in

Table 1 show that the total number of 1, 28, 14,377 GST tax payer in India as on 28.02.2019. Out of them transited or migrated tax payer are 66, 25,077. Total number of new applications for registration are 74,89,804 out of this 63,82,804 applications were accepted remaining applications were rejected. 17, 74,374 GST tax payer opted composition scheme as on 28.02.2018.

2.2 Total Revenue Collection of Goods and Service Tax (GST) As on 28.02.2019

Table 2 and chart 1 clearly exhibits that the total amount of revenue collection of Goods and Services Tax (GST) month wise (Rs in Thousand Crore) from its implementation to as on 28.02.2019 in India. Totally 18, 11,442(Rs in Thousand Crore) collected during the period. Out of this fourteen months are having collection of more than five percentage of total GST collection in India. Out of twenty months positive growth having in eleven month and negative growth having nine months compared with previous month collections.

Table 2 : Total Revenue Collection of Goods and Service Tax (GST) As on 28.02.2019

S. No.	Revenue Collected in the Month of	Amount (in Rs. Thousand crore)	% Total GST As on 28th February, 2019	% (+/-) compared with previous month
1	July, 2017	21,572	1.19	-
2	August, 2017	95,633	5.28	343.32
3	September,2017	94,064	5.19	-1.64
4	October, 2017	93,333	5.15	-0.78
5	November, 2017	83,780	4.63	-10.24
6	December, 2017	84,314	4.65	0.64
7	January, 2018	89,825	4.96	6.54
8	February, 2018	85,962	4.75	-4.30
9	March, 2018	92,167	5.09	7.22
10	April, 2018	1,03,458	5.71	12.25
11	May, 2018	94,016	5.19	-9.13
12	June, 2018	95,610	5.28	1.70
13	July, 2018	96,483	5.33	0.91
14	August, 2018	93,960	5.19	-2.61
15	September, 2018	94,442	5.21	0.51
16	October, 2018	1,00,710	5.56	6.64
17	November, 2018	97,637	5.39	-3.05
18	December, 2018	94,726	5.23	-2.98
19	January,2019	1,02,503	5.66	8.21
20	February, 2019	97,247	5.37	-5.13
Total		18,11,442	100	

Source: www.cbic.gov.in

2.3 Total Number of 3 (B) & GSTR 1 Returns Filed in Goods & Service Tax as on 28.02.2019

Table 3 and chart 2 shows that total numbers of 3(B) and GSTR-1 returns were filed in GST as on 28.02.2019 in India. Starting from July 2017 to January 2019 totally nineteen months results shows that total numbers of 3(B) returns were filed in GST tax payer has increasing trend in fifteen months decreasing trend only in four months compare with previous month tax payers. Total numbers of GSTR-1 returns were filed in GST tax payer has positive growth in ten months negative growth only in nine months compare with previous month tax payers.

Table 3 : Total Number of 3 (B) and GSTR 1 Returns filed in GST as on 28.02.2019

S. No.	Month and Year	Total Returns Filed as on 28.02. 2019			
		3 (B) Returns	compared with previous month	GSTR 1 returns	compared with previous month
		Numbers	% (+/-)	Numbers	% (+/-)
1	July, 2017	6554375	-	6003363	-
2	August, 2017	7125772	8.72	2501312	-58.33
3	September,2017	7462334	4.72	6748642	169.80
4	October, 2017	7212281	-3.35	2576123	-61.83
5	November, 2017	7286703	1.03	2610873	1.35
6	December, 2017	7362714	1.04	6817860	161.13
7	January, 2018	7466460	1.41	2605365	-61.79
8	February, 2018	7577482	1.49	2606304	0.04
9	March, 2018	7667805	1.19	6927768	165.81
10	April, 2018	7694460	0.35	2728772	-60.61
11	May, 2018	7818233	1.61	2748617	0.73
12	June, 2018	7897701	1.02	7048521	156.44
13	July, 2018	7957565	0.76	2750521	-60.98
14	August, 2018	8014906	0.72	2728177	-0.81
15	September, 2018	8041279	0.33	6998553	156.53
16	October, 2018	8052558	0.14	2653997	-62.08
17	November, 2018	7913241	-1.73	2583371	-2.66
18	December, 2018	7818108	-1.20	6436328	149.14
19	January,2019	7348324	-6.01	2183680	-66.07

Source: www.cbic.gov.in

2.4 Total Number of GSTR 4 returns filed in Goods and Service Tax (GST) as on 28.02.2019

Table 4 Total Number of GSTR 4 returns filed Quarterly in Goods and Service Tax (GST) As on 28.02.2019

S. No.	Quarter & Year	GSTR 4 returns filed as on 28th February, 2019	
		Number	% (+/-) compared with Previous Quarter
1	July-September, 2017	9,92,729	-
2	October-December, 2017	14,91,561	50.25
3	January-March, 2018	15,42,871	3.44
4	April-June, 2018	15,06,595	-2.35
5	July-September, 2018	14,53,121	-3.55
6	October-December, 2018	13,71,088	-5.65

Source: www.cbic.gov.in

Table 4 and chart shows that total number of GSTR-4 returns filed quarterly. It shows that July 2017 to September 2017 quarter 9, 92,729 were filed and followed by next quarter 14, 91,561 were filed. The last quarter 13, 71,088 were filed and shows negative growth (-5.65%) comparing with last quarter.

3. Inferential statistical tools Results - Paired Samples T-Test Statistics results

The table 5 indicated that results of paired samples t-test statistics. Totally nine hypotheses were tested and seven variables used in the study.

Table 5 : Paired Samples T-Test Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	VAR 1	7593279.00	19	388571.63	89144.44
	VAR 2	4118849.84	19	2049412.15	470167.39
Pair 2	VAR 3	90220.79	19	17465.39	4006.84
	VAR 1	7593279.00	19	388571.63	89144.44
Pair 3	VAR 3	90220.79	19	17465.39	4006.84
	VAR 2	4118849.84	19	2049412.15	470167.39
Pair 4	VAR 4	22820662.83	6	1135504.26	463567.67
	VAR 5	12679077.83	6	1299806.27	530643.69
Pair 5	VAR 4	22820662.83	6	1135504.26	463567.67
	VAR 7	1392994.17	6	204641.62	83544.59
Pair 6	VAR 5	12679077.83	6	1299806.27	530643.69
	VAR 7	1392994.17	6	204641.62	83544.59
Pair 7	VAR 4	22820662.83	6	1135504.26	463567.67
	VAR 6	268615.33	6	30991.31	12652.15
Pair 8	VAR 5	12679077.83	6	1299806.27	530643.69
	VAR 6	268615.33	6	30991.31	12652.15
Pair 9	VAR 7	1392994.17	6	204641.62	83544.59
	VAR 6	268615.33	6	30991.31	12652.15

Paired Samples Correlations results

The table 6 shows that results of paired samples correlations. Totally nine hypotheses were tested and seven variables used in the study.

Table 6 : Paired Samples Correlations

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	VAR 1 & VAR 2	19	-0.015	0.952
Pair 2	VAR 3 & VAR 1	19	0.700	0.001
Pair 3	VAR 3 & VAR 2	19	-0.273	0.258
Pair 4	VAR 4 & VAR 5	6	-0.666	0.149
Pair 5	VAR 4 & VAR 7	6	0.584	0.224
Pair 6	VAR 5 & VAR 7	6	-0.891	0.017
Pair 7	VAR 4 & VAR 6	6	0.913	0.011
Pair 8	VAR 5 & VAR 6	6	-0.864	0.026
Pair 9	VAR 7 & VAR 6	6	0.800	0.056

3.1 Hypotheses Testing- 1

(1) Null and Alternative Hypotheses

The following null and alternative hypotheses need to be tested:

H₀: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no difference between total number of 3(B) returned filed GST tax payers and GSTR1 returned filed GST tax payers for month wise as on 28.02.2109.

H0 $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no difference between total number of 3(B) returned filed GST tax payers and GSTR1 returned filed GST tax payers for month wise as on 28.02.2109.

This corresponds to a two-tailed test, for which a t-test for two paired samples be used.

(2) **Test Statistics:** The t-statistic is computed as shown in $t = 7.241$

(3) **Decision about the null hypothesis**

Since it is observed that $[t] = 7.241 > t_c = 2.101$, it is then concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p = 0$ and since $p = 0 < 0.05$, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected.

(4) **Conclusion**

It is concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that population mean μ_1 is different than μ_2 , at the 0.05 significance level.

3.2 Paired t Test Hypotheses Testing- 2

(1) **Null and Alternative Hypotheses**

The following null and alternative hypotheses need to be tested:

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no difference between Total GST Revenue collected from tax payers and total number of 3(B) returned filed GST tax payers for month wise as on 28.02.2109.

H0 $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is difference between Total GST Revenue collected from tax payers and total number of 3(B) returned filed GST tax payers for month wise as on 28.02.2109.

(2) **Test Statistics:** The t-statistic is computed as shown in $t = -86.853$

(3) **Decision about the null hypothesis**

Since it is observed that $[t] = 86.853 > t_c = 2.101$, it is then concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p = 0$, and since $p = 0 < 0.05$, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected.

(4) **Conclusion**

It is concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that population mean μ_1 is different than μ_2 , at the 0.05 significance level.

3.3 Hypotheses Testing- 3

(1) **Null and Alternative Hypotheses**

The following null and alternative hypotheses need to be tested:

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no difference between total GST Revenue collected from tax payers and total number of GSTR1 returned filed GST tax payers for month wise as on 28.02.2109.

H0 $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is difference between total GST Revenue collected from tax payers and total number of GSTR1 returned filed GST tax payers for month wise as on 28.02.2109.

This corresponds to a two-tailed test, for which a t-test for two paired samples be used.

(2) **Test Statistics:** The t-statistic is computed as shown in $t = -8.548$.

(3) **Decision about the null hypothesis**

Since it is observed that $[t] = 8.548 > t_c = 2.101$, it is then concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p = 0$, and since $p = 0 < 0.05$, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected.

(4) **Conclusion**

It is concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that population mean μ_1 is different than μ_2 , at the 0.05 significance level.

3.4 Hypotheses Testing- 4

(1) **Null and Alternative Hypotheses**

The following null and alternative hypotheses need to be tested:

$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no difference between total number of 3(b) return filed and total number of GSTR1 return filed in quarter wise by GST tax payers as on 28.02.2109.

$H_0 \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is difference between total number of 3(b) return filed and total number of GSTR1 return filed in quarter wise by GST tax payers as on 28.02.2109.

This corresponds to a two-tailed test, for which a t-test for two paired samples be used.

(2) **Test Statistics:** The t-statistic is computed as shown in $t = 11.172$

(3) **Decision about the null hypothesis**

Since it is observed that $[t] = 11.172 > t_c = 2.571$, it is then concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p = 0.0001$, and since $p = 0.0001 < 0.05$, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected.

(4) **Conclusion**

It is concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that population mean μ_1 is different than μ_2 , at the 0.05 significance level.

3.5 Hypotheses Testing- 5

(1) **Null and Alternative Hypotheses**

The following null and alternative hypotheses need to be tested:

$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no difference between total number of 3(b) return filed and total number of GSTR 4 return filed in quarter wise by GST tax payers as on 28.02.2109.

$H_0 \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is difference between total number of 3(b) return filed and total number of GSTR 4 return filed in quarter wise by GST tax payers as on 28.02.2109.

This corresponds to a two-tailed test, for which a t-test for two paired samples be used.

(2) **Test Statistics:** The t-statistic is computed as shown in $t=50.983$

(3) **Decision about the null hypothesis**

Since it is observed that $[t]=50.983 > t_c=2.571$, it is then concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p=0$, and since $p=0 < 0.05$, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected.

(4) **Conclusion**

It is concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that population mean μ_1 is different than μ_2 , at the 0.05 significance level.

3.6 Hypotheses Testing- 6

(1) **Null and Alternative Hypotheses**

The following null and alternative hypotheses need to be tested:

$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no difference between total number of GSTR 1 return filed and total number of GSTR 4 return filed in quarter wise by GST tax payers as on 28.02.2109.

$H_0 \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is difference between total number of GSTR 1 return filed and total number of GSTR 4 return filed in quarter wise by GST tax payers as on 28.02.2109.

This corresponds to a two-tailed test, for which a t-test for two paired samples be used.

(2) **Test Statistics**

The t-statistic is computed as shown in $t= 18.615$

(3) **Decision about the null hypothesis**

Since it is observed that $[t]=18.615 > t_c=2.571$, it is then concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p=0$, and since $p=0 < 0.05$, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected.

(4) **Conclusion**

It is concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that population mean μ_1 is different than μ_2 , at the 0.05 significance level.

3.7 Hypotheses Testing- 7

(1) **Null and Alternative Hypotheses**

The following null and alternative hypotheses need to be tested:

$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no difference between total number of 3(B) returned filed and total GST Revenue collected from tax payers by quarter wise as on 28.02.2109.

$H_0 \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is difference between total number of 3(B) returned filed and total GST Revenue collected from tax payers by quarter wise as on 28.02.2109.

This corresponds to a two-tailed test, for which a t-test for two paired samples be used.

(2) **Test Statistics:** The t-statistic is computed as shown in $t=49.889$.

(3) **Decision about the null hypothesis**

Since it is observed that $[t]=49.889 > t_c=2.571$, it is then concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p=0$, and since $p=0 < 0.05$, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected.

(4) **Conclusion**

It is concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that population mean μ_1 is different than μ_2 , at the 0.05 significance level.

3.8 Hypotheses Testing-8

(1) **Null and Alternative Hypotheses**

The following null and alternative hypotheses need to be tested:

$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no difference between total number of GSTR4 returned filed and total GST Revenue collected from tax payers by quarter wise as on 28.02.2109.

$H_0 \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is difference between total number of GSTR4 returned filed and total GST Revenue collected from tax payers by quarter wise as on 28.02.2109.

This corresponds to a two-tailed test, for which a t-test for two paired samples be used.

(2) **Test Statistics:** The t-statistic is computed as shown in $t=22.914$.

(3) **Decision about the null hypothesis**

Since it is observed that $[t]=22.914 > t_c=2.571$, it is then concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p=0$, and since $p=0 < 0.05$, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected.

(4) **Conclusion**

It is concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that population mean μ_1 is different than μ_2 , at the 0.05 significance level.

3.9 Hypotheses Testing-9

(1) **Null and Alternative Hypotheses**

The following null and alternative hypotheses need to be tested:

$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no difference between total of GSTR4 returned filed and total GST Revenue collected from tax payers by quarter wise as on 28.02.2109.

$H_0 \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is difference between total number of GSTR4 returned filed and total GST Revenue collected from tax payers by quarter wise as on 28.02.2109.

This corresponds to a two-tailed test, for which a t-test for two paired samples be used.

(2) **Test Statistics:** The t-statistic is computed as shown in $t=15.233$

(3) Decision about the null hypothesis

Since it is observed $[t]=15.233 > t_c=2.571$, it is then concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p=0$, and since $p=0 < 0.05$, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected.

(4) Conclusion

It is concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that population mean μ_1 is different than μ_2 , at the 0.05 significance level.

Table 7 Paired Samples t Test

Variables		Paired Differences						t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Results of Hypotheses Testing
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference						
					Lower	Upper					
Pair 1	VAR1 - VAR2	3474429.16	2091609.16	479848.05	2466305.81	4482552.50	7.24	18	0.00	Difference	
Pair 2	VAR3 - VAR1	-7503058.21	376557.51	86388.22	-7684553.12	-7321563.30	-86.85	18	0.00	Difference	
Pair 3	VAR3 - VAR2	-4028629.05	2054253.13	471277.99	-5018747.37	-3038510.74	-8.55	18	0.00	Difference	
Pair 4	VAR4 - VAR5	10141585.00	2223639.33	907796.95	7808018.64	12475151.36	11.17	5	0.00	Difference	
Pair 5	VAR4 - VAR7	21427668.67	1029489.03	420287.13	20347286.19	22508051.14	50.98	5	0.00	Difference	
Pair 6	VAR5 - VAR7	11286083.67	1485080.64	606281.63	9727587.11	12844580.22	18.62	5	0.00	Difference	
Pair 7	VAR4 - VAR6	22552047.50	1107289.17	452048.91	21390018.79	23714076.21	49.89	5	0.00	Difference	
Pair 8	VAR5 - VAR6	12410462.50	1326677.43	541613.79	11018199.92	13802725.08	22.91	5	0.00	Difference	
Pair 9	VAR7 - VAR6	1124378.83	180807.53	73814.37	934632.96	1314124.70	15.23	5	0.00	Difference	
* variables used											
VAR1	Number of 3 B return filed in month wise										
VAR2	Number of GSTR-1 return filed in month wise										
VAR3	Revenue collected in month wise(Rs in Thousands Crore) in month wise										
VAR4	Number of 3 B return filed in Quarter Wise										
VAR5	Number of GSTR-1 return filed in Quarter Wise										
VAR6	Revenue collected in month wise(Rs in Thousands Crore) in Quarter Wise										
VAR7	Number of GSTR-4 return filed in Quarter Wise										

Conclusion

This research study results shows that total number of 1, 28, 14,377 GST tax payer in India. Out of them transited or migrated tax payer are 66, 25,077. Total number of new applications for registration are 74,89,804 out of this 63,82,804 applications were accepted. 10,53,602 applications were rejected. 17, 74,374 GST tax payer opted composition scheme as on 28.02.2018. Totally 18, 11,442(Rs in Thousand Crore) collected during the period. Out of this fourteen months are having collection of more than five percentage of total GST collection in India. Out of twenty months positive growth having in eleven month and negative growth having nine months compared with previous month collections.

This study results also reveals that total numbers of 3(B) returns were filed in GST tax payer has increasing trend in fifteen months decreasing trend only in four months compare with previous month tax payers. Total numbers of GSTR-1 returns were filed in GST tax payer has positive growth in ten months negative growth only in nine months compare with previous month tax payers. This study finally suggested that government of India, ministry of finance, ministry of commerce and various State/UT governments to take necessary reforms in GST registrations, filing of GST return, payment of tax, refund, interest, penalty and various types GST exemptions different type of tax payers. It is finally concluded that the introduction of GST in India has replaced all indirect taxes in one tax and common market for entire nation it will bring positive energy for entrepreneurs for starting new business ventures in India.

References

- Barhate G.H(2017). Study of Awareness and Perception towards GST amongst Traders in Rural Areas, IRJET,1133-1142.
- Rajesh Chadha (2009).Moving to Goods and Services Tax in India: Impact on India's Growth and International Trade, NCAER,1-78
- Rupa.R(2017). GST in India: an overview, IERJ, 88-89.
- Saurabh Gupta, Sarita ,Munindra kumar, Komal and Hemraj Kumawat(2017).Good and Service Tax: An International Comparative Analysis, IJRFM, 164-173.
- S.Kawle1 and Yogesh.L.Aher (2017).GST: An economic overview: Challenges and Impact ahead, IRJET, 2760-2763.
- Rekha & Dev Karan (2018).An Overview of Goods and Services Tax (GST) In India, International Journal of Business and Management,13-18
- Rajesh Desai and Ankit Patel(2015).Goods and services tax in India: an opportunities and challenges, IJCR, 23347-23349.
- Karteek Madapana, and Kotini Avinash Gupta(2016).A Review on Goods and services tax (GST): A panacea for Indian economy & its impact on various sectors, IJMER,12-15.
- ASSOCHAM(2015).Goods and Services Tax in India Taking stock and setting expectations, Deloitte,1-25.
- Anand Nayyar and Inderpal Singh (2018).A Comprehensive Analysis of Goods and Services Tax (GST) in India, IJF,51-71

- Pranesh Debnath(2016).Implementation of Goods and Service Tax (GST) in India and its Control over the Tax Collection, JCT, 28-33.
- SANKAR (2017).GST: Impact and Implications on Various Industries in Indian Economy, Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce, 1-9
- Surendra S. Yadav, Ravi Shankar, (2018).Goods and service tax (GST): how and why, Journal of Advances in Management Research, Vol. 15 Issue: 1, 2-3.
- Satya Poddar and Ehtisham Ahmad(2009).GST Reforms and Intergovernmental Considerations in India, Working Paper No.1/2009-DEA,1-45.
- Goutam Bhattacharya(2017). Evaluation and implementation of GST in Indian growth: A study, IJCMR, 65-68.
- Sacchidananda Mukherjee(2015).Present State of Goods and Services Tax (GST) Reform in India, WPNo. 2015-154, NIPFP, New Delhi,1-24.
- Milandeep Kour, Kajal Chaudhary, Surjan Singh and Baljinder Kaur(2016). A Study on Impact of GST after Its Implementation, IJISSH,17-24.
- Jose Sebastian (2017).Goods and Services Tax: Rationale, Relevance and Implications for India's Fiscal Federalism, Policy Dialogue Series, WP1, ISDG, 1-23.
- PhD Research Bureau.Goods and Service Tax (GST) impact on economy history and people, PhD Chamber of Commerce, New Delhi,1-33.
- Lourdunathan F and Xavier (2017).Study on implementation of goods and services tax (GST) in India: Prospectus and challenges, IJAR, 626-629.
- Anand Deo(2017). Goods & Services Tax (GST) – Impact analysis &road ahead, IBMRD's Journal of Management & Research, 17-28.
- Yogesh Kailashchandra Agrawal(2017). Goods and Services Tax and Its Impact on Indian Economy, 26-30.
- Shilpa Rani(2017). A research paper on goods and service tax (GST) and its impact on Indian economy, IJAR, 209-212
- Dash A (2017). Positive and Negative Impact of GST on Indian Economy, IJMAS,159-160
- Vasanthagopal R (2011).GST in India: A Big Leap in the Indirect Taxation System, IJTEF, 144-146.
- Venugopal Reddy(2017). A Study on Prospects and Challenges in Implementation of Goods and Services Tax (GST) in India, IOSR JBMt, 31-34.
- Ehtisham Ahmad and Satya Poddar(2009).GST Reforms And Intergovernmental Considerations In India, Asia Research Centre WP 26,1-43.
- Sthanu R. Nair & Leena Mary Eapen(2017). Goods and Services Tax and Price Control Measures: Lessons for India from Australian Experience, W.P.IIMK/WPS/227/EA/2017/11.
- Subhamoy Banik and Arundhuti Das (2017).GST in India: Impact and challenges, IOSR Journal of Business and Management,07-10.

- Esha Bansal(2018). A Study on Impact of GST on Indian Economy, International Journal of Research and Innovation in Applied Science, 17-20.
- Kankipati Ajay Kumar (2017).A Journey of Goods and Services Tax (GST) and Structural Impact of GST on the Growth of GDP in India, Advances in Sciences and Humanities, 50-53
- Pramod Kumar Pandey(2017). The Impact of Indian Taxation system on its Economic Growth, SSARSC IJM,1-8.
- Jadhav Bhika Lala(2017).Impact of GST on Indian economy, IJRSR,17505-17508.
- RaghuramK.S and Deepa(2015). Goods and Services Tax: The Introduction Process, W.P. No.2015-03-01, IIM, Ahmedabad,1-43.
- Naresh Kumar (2018).Goods and Services Tax (GST): Networking and its working process, IJRDO-JBM, 27-40.
- Prasad & S. S. Singh (2017). Services Sector: Challenges, Issues and Policy Suggestion with special focus on IT-BPM, Tourism, Shipping, Real Estate Services and Project Exports, WP No. 2/2017-DEA, GOI, MOF, 1-51
- Sachin Abda(2017).Research Paper on Effects of Goods and Services Tax on Indian Economy, IERJ,584-5485.
- Mohapatrar., Joliyap., Kamalvanshi V.and Kushwaha S (2018).Perception of GST in Varanasi district of Uttar Pradesh, International Journal of Agriculture Sciences, 7369-7371
- Mohamad Ali Roshidi Ahmad, ZuriadahIsmail, and Hazianti Abdul Halim(2016). Awareness and Perception of Taxpayers towards Goods and Services Tax (GST) Implementation, IJARBSS,75-93.
- Pallavi Chaturvedi and Suruchi Madan(2017). Goods and Service Tax: A Game Changer for Indian Economy, JCECS, 305-308
- Azharuddin Mohammad Mussaiyib (2016).Goods and Services Tax in India: An Insight, IJRIAS,11-15.
- Chandu Ravi Kumar (2015).GST in Indian Economy: It's Benefits and Impact, IJSR,759-761.
- Dash (2017).Positive and negative impact of GST on Indian economy, International JMAs, 160-162